

COMPLEMENTARY SERIES AND CONJUGATE FRAGMENTS IN URANIUM FISSION*

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The fission yield values have been utilised in identifying complementary series in uranium fission. It has been concluded that the two series, whose yield values have got approximately identical positions in the yield-mass curves, are complementary to each other. From the complementary series thus identified, conjugate fragments, which are responsible for a pair of chains in question, have been sorted out. The view that a complementary series is solely due to the β -decays of a single pair of initial primary fragments has been shown to be erroneous in the light of practical experience. It has been argued that each and every nucleus in a pair of complementary series has not only a primary origin but the yield in each case is made up of the primary fission and the β -decays of the predecessors. Different probable modes of fission in between the stable members of each pairs of a complementary series, with an assumption that the sum of the charges of the two conjugate fragments in each case is 92, has been considered. It has been argued that fission probabilities of all processes of primary formation in a pair of complementary series are not equal. The main contribution to the yield is due to one pair of conjugate fragments. The mass/charge values of this most probable pair are approximately equal. The fission frequency of the other conjugate fragments gets less and less and merges beyond the range of experimental observation as the mass/charge values of the conjugate fragments diverge from this equivalent point. The general feature of a complementary series may be pictured as follows :

in which $(117-m)$ and $(117+m)$ stand for mass numbers of light and heavy nuclei respectively and $(46-c)$ and $(46+c)$ represent the respective charge numbers. The most probable conjugate fragments in each complementary series have been found out. From practical evidences it has been argued that in a chain at least three consecutive isobars with charge numbers either lower or higher than that of the most probable fragment may be expected. On this basis the total number of active nuclei (in between mass numbers 76 and 158) expected in fission are 549 and only 165 among these have been so far known.

As a result of rapid progress in the study of nuclear fission, 170 active isotopes of 35 elements from ${}_{30}Zn$ to ${}_{64}Gd$ have now been discovered (Plutonium Project Report, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 2411). The mass numbers of the isotopes range from 72 to 158 and indicate the presence of 87 radioactive chains. A chain is provisionally termed light when its mass number is either equal to or below 117, and heavy when its mass number lies above 117. We have 46 radioactive chains in the light group and 41 chains fall in the heavy group. It is an established fact that corresponding to a chain in the light group there is a chain in the heavy group. But the observations so far recorded from the ionisation and cloud chamber studies are such that we are confronted with a mass phenomenon involving huge number of different fission processes and as such we cannot trace the individual complementary chains and after that cannot sort out the conjugate fragments which are responsible for the complementary chains in question. The object of the present investigation is to find out the individual complementary series

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from an analytical study of the yield-mass curve (Fig. 1) and to sort out the conjugate fragments due to which the complementary series in question have been formed.

A typical fission process can be symbolically written as follows :—

$A_1 = 117 - m$, $A_2 = 117 + m$, $A_1 + A_2 = 234$ as shown later, m has been found to vary from 0 to 41; $Z_1 + Z_2 = 92$. $A_1 + A_2 + x = 236$, $x =$ number of neutrons released which is shown in this paper to be 2. The chain A_1 may be termed the light chain and A_2 , the heavy chain. Each primary product of fission A_1 and A_2 undergoes successive β -disintegrations till it ends in stable atoms: $(Z_1 + n_1) MA_1$ and $(Z_2 + n_2) MA_2$.

The two chains (A_1 and A_2) arising out of any one act of fission, as pictured above, may be said to be "conjugate". The two nuclei, $Z_1 MA_1$ and $Z_2 MA_2$ ($Z_1 + Z_2 = 92$), which are initially produced in a pair of conjugate chains may be termed conjugate fragments. The mass numbers A_1 and A_2 may be designated as complementary numbers. It has been shown subsequently that each of the members, namely $(Z_1 + 1) MA_1$, $(Z_1 + 2) MA_1$ etc. and $(Z_2 + 1) MA_2$, $(Z_2 + 2) MA_2$ etc. in addition to its being produced by β -disintegration of the predecessor, is also formed as a primary fragment; and conjugate nuclei like $(Z_1 + 1) MA_1$, $(Z_2 - 1) MA_2$; $(Z_1 - 1) MA_1$, $(Z_2 + 1) MA_2$ etc. may be produced. The pair of chains that we observe with complementary numbers A_1 and A_2 are then due to a number of conjugate chains as defined above, and such a pair may be termed complementary chains or series.

In Fig. 1, the logarithms of the fission yield has been plotted against mass numbers. In Table I, the fission yields have been arranged in a way and in order so that approximately identical yields with corresponding light and heavy mass numbers fall in the same columns. The data have been taken from the report of a lecture delivered by A. V. Grosse (*Chem. Eng. News*, 1947, 25, 1509).

From the yield-mass curve (Fig. 1) we note the following points:

(1) The two exactly similar and identical curves, one due to light mass numbers from 72 up to 116 and the other due to heavy mass numbers from 118 upwards up to 158, appear to meet at the point due to mass number 117. The two curves are so much exactly similar that the whole figure can be folded about the mass line 117.

(2) Both the curves rise at first steeply as we pass from lower mass number to higher mass numbers in the light group and higher to lower mass numbers in the heavy group and then in both the cases the rate of rise falls, as a result there are two humps, after which there are steep falls which are again followed by flattened portions and ultimately the two curves meet at yield point due to mass number 117.

(3) The total per cent of yield in the light series is approximately equal to that in the heavy series. (The two together are twice the per cent of fission due to which the light and the heavy nuclei have been formed).

Fig. 1

TABLE I

L i g h t		H e a v y		L i g h t		H e a v y	
Mass.	Yield.	Yield.	Mass.	Mass.	Yield.	Yield.	Mass.
72	1.5×10^{-5}			95	6.4	6.3	139
73	1.0×10^{-4}			96	6.6	6.3	138
74	2.0×10^{-4}			97	6.6	6.3	137
75	8.0×10^{-4}			98	6.4	6.1	136
76	2.0×10^{-3}	2.0×10^{-3}	158	99	6.2	6.0	135
77	9.1×10^{-3}	7.4×10^{-3}	157	100	5.8	5.2	134
78	2.0×10^{-2}	1.6×10^{-2}	156	101	5.2	4.5	133
79	4.0×10^{-2}	3.0×10^{-2}	155	102	4.6	3.6	132
80	8.0×10^{-2}	1.0×10^{-1}	154	103	3.7	2.6	131
81	1.3×10^{-1}	1.5×10^{-1}	153	104	2.6	1.7	130
82	2.5×10^{-1}	3.8×10^{-1}	152	105	9.0×10^{-1}	1.00	129
83	4.0×10^{-1}	6.0×10^{-1}	151	106	5.0×10^{-1}	4.0×10^{-1}	128
84	6.5×10^{-1}	1.0	150	107	2.0×10^{-1}	1.8×10^{-1}	127
85	1.2	1.4	149	108	1.0×10^{-1}	3.0×10^{-2}	126
86	2.0	2.0	148	109	2.8×10^{-2}	2.3×10^{-2}	125
87	2.8	2.6	147	110	1.7×10^{-2}	2.0×10^{-2}	124
88	3.7	3.5	146	111	1.3×10^{-2}	1.7×10^{-2}	123
89	4.6	4.5	145	112	1.21×10^{-2}	1.5×10^{-2}	122
90	5.0	5.2	144	113	1.1×10^{-2}	1.4×10^{-2}	121
91	5.4	5.5	143	114	1.0×10^{-2}	1.3×10^{-2}	120
92	5.8	5.8	142	115	1.0×10^{-2}	1.2×10^{-2}	119
93	6.1	5.9	141	116	1.0×10^{-2}	1.1×10^{-2}	118
94	6.3	6.2	140	117	1.0×10^{-2}		

(4) It is further obvious that corresponding to a light point, there is a heavy point with almost identical yield (which may be taken to be the same within experimental error), e. g., 84 and 150. We can trace such complementary numbers from 76 to 117 on the light side and corresponding ones from 158 to 117 on the heavy side. In the light series, we start with mass number 72, but no heavy mass numbers complementary to 72 and for higher numbers up to 75, have yet been found in the heavy group. This is partly due to low fission frequency of this type of fission and partly due to difficulty encountered in the separation of the rare-earths which are the most probable nuclei in this region or it may so happen that these mass numbers result from ternary fission. The mass numbers from 72 to 75 have not been shown in Fig. 1 for want of accommodation.

(5) The sum of the two mass numbers which have approximately identical positions in the yield-mass curve is always 234.

From the facts pointed out above the following conclusions can be arrived at:

(1) As far as fissions with slow neutrons are concerned, each series in the light group has a complementary series in the heavy group.

(2) Two series are complementary when their positions in the yield-mass curves are approximately identical. For instance, the series due to mass number 76 has identical yield and has position identical with that of mass number 158 and so these two are complementary. From these two extreme ends (at 76 and 158) as we pass from mass number to mass number, each pair represents units of complementary series till the point representing the series with mass number 117 from both the sides is approached. This series (with mass 117) represents a case of symmetrical fission. So the general equation for series in nuclear fission will be as follows :

where the values of m varies from 0 to 41 (as far as observation goes).

'How to find out the conjugate fragments' is the second aspect of this investigation. Fission nuclei form long chains of β -disintegrating series. At the first sight it seems that all the isobars in the series have been formed by successive β -disintegration of an isobar of lower nuclear charge. From this point of view, the birth of a pair of complementary series is due to the fissions of uranium nucleus into two conjugate fragments in a way so that the sum of the charges of the two nuclei is 92; these two primary fragments by successive β -disintegrations give rise to the complementary series in question and all other nuclei excepting these two primaries are of secondary origin.

But there are no evidences for the existence of two primary fragments. Even if we identify a series to be complementary to another by the equivalence of yield values, as suggested by us, we cannot find out the exact point of division (as regards charge) where a uranium nucleus breaks up if we are guided by the idea that a series in question has been formed only by successive β -disintegration of a single nucleus. For instance, the series which starts with $54 \text{ Xe } 145$ is complementary to the series which seems to start from $36 \text{ Kr } 89$ as far as yield/mass values are concerned. If we assume that $36 \text{ Kr } 89$ is a primary product then $56 \text{ Ba } 145$ should also be primary but $56 \text{ Ba } 145$ has been shown to grow from $54 \text{ Xe } 145 \rightarrow 55 \text{ Cs } 145 \rightarrow 56 \text{ Ba } 145$; similarly if $54 \text{ Xe } 145$ is supposed to be a primary product, the conjugate primary fragment shall be $38 \text{ Sr } 89$, but $38 \text{ Sr } 89$ has been shown to grow from $36 \text{ Kr } 89 \rightarrow 37 \text{ Rb } 89 \rightarrow 38 \text{ Sr } 89$. Even putting aside the idea of complementary series, if we assume that some krypton isotopes are primary, there must be at least some corresponding barium isotopes which should also be primary, but all the barium isotopes detected in fission are found to be formed by β -decay of 55 Cs . Similarly if 54 Xe isotopes are supposed to be primary, the corresponding isotopes in the light group *i. e.*, isotopes of 38 Sr should be primary, but all the isotopes of 38 Sr detected in fission have been found to be formed by β -decay of the predecessors. The series headed by kryptons and xenons constitute 89% of the total fission yield (200%) but their origin cannot be explained by supposition that the existence of so many isobars in a series is only due to the successive β -decay of a single isobar of lower nuclear charge. Similarly, for instance, if we take 35 Br as primary in the series which have been observed to start

from ^{35}Br , we must have ^{57}La as a primary particle, but all the lanthanum isotopes observed in fission have been shown to grow from their corresponding predecessors. It should be pointed out that isobars with comparatively low nuclear charge in a series are short lived and their detections up to xenons and kryptons in the regions concerned have been only possible due to bubbling method developed by Hahn (*Naturwiss.*, 1939, **27**, 89, 163, 529). It seems that all other series can also be extended to isobars of lower nuclear charge provided experimental technique facilitating their detections is developed.

In addition to evidences set forth above it has been observed (Plutonium Project Report, *loc. cit.*) that in a series an isobar with lower nuclear charge has an yield lower than that of an isobar with higher nuclear charge (Table II) and that in some cases a β -active nucleus of low fission yield with a nuclear charge higher than that of a stable member of the series has also been discovered (*cf.* Table III).

TABLE II

Mass No.	Nuclei.	Yield %.	Mass No.	Nuclei.	Yield %.
77	$^{32}\text{Ge } 77$ ↓ $^{33}\text{As } 77$	0.0037 0.0091	83	$^{34}\text{Se } 83$ ↓ $^{35}\text{Br } 83$	0.21 0.41 0.31
Mass No.	Nuclei.	Yield %.	Mass No.	Nuclei.	Yield %.
91	$^{38}\text{Sr } 91$ ↓ $^{39}\text{Y } 91$	5.0 5.9	135	$^{53}\text{I } 135$ ↓ $^{54}\text{Xe } 135$	5.6 5.9
				$^{56}\text{Ba } 141$ ↓ $^{57}\text{La } 141$ ↓ $^{58}\text{Ce } 141$	4.6 5.7

TABLE III

Stable isobar in a series with lower nuclear charge.		β -Active isobar with higher nuclear charge.			Expected conjugate fragments in the complementary series.
Nuclei.	Series yield%.	Nuclei.	Half life.	Yield %.	
$^{34}\text{Se } 82$	2.5×10^{-1}	$^{35}\text{Br } 82$	34 hrs.	2.8×10^{-5}	$^{57}\text{La } 152$
$^{36}\text{Kr } 86$	2.0	$^{37}\text{Rb } 86$	19.5 days	1.6×10^{-4}	$^{55}\text{Cs } 148$
$^{54}\text{Xe } 136$	6.1	$^{55}\text{Cs } 136$	13.0 days	0.01	$^{37}\text{Rb } 136$

From the observations as stated above it is clear that the view that a uranium nucleus breaks up solely into two primary fragments and these two primaries by successive β -disintegrations give rise to a complementary series and that all other nuclei excepting a single primary in a series are solely secondary, is absolutely wrong. On the other hand, these observations seem to suggest that possibly each isobar in a series is derived from both primary and secondary origins. As for instance, the products with mass number 76 and that with 158 have got identical yield and as such are complementary to each other in fission. All possible modes of fission including stable members of both the groups are represented below (Scheme 1).

SCHEME 1

Conjugate chains in a complementary series.

It appears from the above equations that all expected nuclei excluding ${}_{60}\text{Nd}_{158}$ and ${}_{28}\text{Ni}_{76}$ (which are regarded provisionally to be primaries) are primary and secondary at the same time and that a nucleus, e.g. stable ${}_{32}\text{Ge } 76$ can originate as a primary fragment in a fission process as given at the head of the figure, but also as a secondary product in a number of ways as illustrated above. The complementary series mentioned above are due to at least five distinct modes of fission of uranium nuclei. Question naturally arises "Do the five pairs of conjugate fragments, as pictured above, contribute equally to the yield of the complementary chain?" The yield values in Tables II and III give a strong indication that each distinct mode of fission into conjugate fragments cannot have equal frequency, and suggest that the main contribution to the yield is due to one pair of conjugate fragments. It has been supposed that the mass/charge ratio values of this particular pair of conjugate fragments are approximately equal and frequency of the other conjugate fragments becomes less and less as the mass/charge ratio values diverge from this equivalent point. In Table IV are given the values of mass/charge ratios of the conjugate fragments as pictured in Scheme 1. In the calculation, one unit of mass in each case has been added to the complementary numbers in consideration of the fact that each one of the conjugate fragment releases one neutron just after fission.

TABLE IV

Eq. No.	76		158	
	L i g h t		H e a v y	
	A/Z.	Values	A_1/Z_1	Values.
(a)	77/32	2.406	159/60	2.650
(b)	77/31	2.481	159/61	2.607
(c)	77/30	2.566	159/62	2.561
(d)	77/29	2.650	159/63	2.524
(e)	77/28	2.735	159/64	2.481

From the values it seems that the frequency is maximum due to equation (c), and as the values of mass/charge ratio of the conjugate fragments diverge from the equivalent point, the corresponding frequency of fission may be supposed to become less and less

till at last the frequency of the conjugate nuclei becomes so small that their yield goes beyond the limit of experimental observations.

From such considerations, as stated above, the most probable charge numbers in each complementary series have been found out. The symmetrical fission has been found to be symmetrical both as regards mass and charge as far as the series with maximum yield is concerned. Hence, a general equation for fission both as regards mass and charge can be written as follows.

where the value of c for the most probable charge numbers varies from 0 to 16.

SCHEME 2

Most probable conjugate chains in a few complementary series.

DISCUSSION

Most Probable Charge Numbers

From what has been said before it appears that there must be a most probable pair of conjugate fragments in a complementary series. Being guided by the ideas that there is a uniform distribution of neutrons and protons in most of the nuclei undergoing fission (Davidson and Watson, *Phys. Rev.*, 1947, **71**, 742) we have assumed that the mass/charge ratio values of the most probable pair are equal. In calculations the values which do not differ by more than 1% have been taken to be equivalent. In some complementary series it has been found that the ratio values differ by near about 3%, and that there is another pair of consecutive conjugate fragments with approximately identical divergence,

as: 96/38, 2.526; 140/54, 2.592; and 96/37, 2.595; 140/55, 2.545. In such cases it has been assumed that there are equal probability of contributions by both the pairs. On this basis a list of equations denoting complementary series corresponding to maximum yield has been derived. A portion of the list has been inserted in Scheme 2.

It will be evident from Scheme 2 that the same element, characterised by a definite charge number, can at best be the most probable fragment in four complementary series. It is further obvious that in case of equal probability of contributions by two pairs of conjugate fragments, the same mass number is found to have two charge numbers as most probable fragments. The most probable conjugate charge numbers with their corresponding mass numbers and the yield of the most probable charge numbers are given in Table V. As the yield of a complementary series is mainly due to the most probable conjugate fragments, so, as a first approximation, the series yield has been assumed to correspond to the yield of the most probable charge number in question. It has already been stated that in some series two charge numbers appear as most probable fragments. In such cases, half of the series yield has been attributed to each charge number. As an illustration let us take a most probable charge number, say 35. From Table V we note that element 35 appears as a most probable fragment for mass numbers 87, 88, 89 and 90. For mass number 87 it shares the yield values with charge number 34, whilst for mass number 90 it shares with charge number 36. So the yield value of charge number 35

$$= \frac{\text{yield (87)}}{2} + \text{yield (88)} + \text{yield (89)} + \frac{\text{yield (90)}}{2}$$

In this way the yield values of most probable conjugate charge numbers have been found out and inserted in Table V. In the table the mass numbers which relate to one most probable fragment have been shown in *italics*.

TABLE V

Most probable charge No.	Mass No.	Light	Heavy	Mass No.	Most probable charge No.
		Yield %.	Yield %.		
30	76, 77	6.06 × 10 ⁻³	5.7 × 10 ⁻³	153, 157	62
31	77, 78, 79, 80	1.00 × 10 ⁻¹	0.997 × 10 ⁻¹	157, 156, 155, 154	61
32	80, 81, 82	3.00 × 10 ⁻¹	3.9 × 10 ⁻¹	154, 153, 152	60
33	82, 83, 84, 85	1.78	2.49	152, 151, 150, 149	59
34	85, 86, 87	4.00	4.00	149, 148, 147	58
35	87, 88, 89, 90	12.2	12.0	147, 146, 145, 144	57
36	90, 91, 92, 93	13.85	13.95	144, 143, 142, 141	56
37	92, 93, 94, 95	15.45	15.15	142, 141, 140, 139	55
38	95, 96, 97, 98	19.06	18.80	139, 138, 137, 136	54
39	98, 99, 100, 101	17.8	16.55	136, 135, 134, 133	53
40	101, 102, 103	9.05	7.20	133, 132, 131	52
41	103, 104, 105, 106	3.15	3.70	131, 130, 129, 128	51
42	105, 106, 107, 108	9.5 × 10 ⁻¹	9.0 × 10 ⁻¹	129, 128, 127, 126	50
43	108, 109, 110, 111	9.3 × 10 ⁻²	6.0 × 10 ⁻²	126, 125, 124, 123	49
44	110, 111, 112, 113	3.25 × 10 ⁻²	3.95 × 10 ⁻²	124, 123, 122, 121	48
45	113, 114, 115, 116	2.55 × 10 ⁻²	3.15 × 10 ⁻²	121, 120, 119, 118	47
46	115, 116, 117	1.5 × 10 ⁻²	1.65 × 10 ⁻²	119, 118, 117	46

In Fig 2, 1/3 of the fission yield% has been plotted against charge numbers.

In Fig. 2, the logarithms of the yields values of the most probable charge numbers have been plotted against charge numbers. The curve is exactly the same as mass *versus* yield curve (Fig. 1). The most probable conjugate charge numbers have nearly equal yield and approximately identical position in the curve.

Fig. 2

Predictions

Long chains of β -disintegrating chains are observed in fission. It has been stated that in a series the yield is due to most probable charge number, so in a chain an isobar with a nuclear charge lower than that of the most probable fragment will have very small yield, while in the case of an isobar with a nuclear charge higher than that of the most probable fragment, the yield will be enhanced by the β -decay of the most probable fragment. From such considerations we note that the most probable charge numbers divide the active isobars in a series into two groups, namely, isobars with nuclear charges lower

than that of the most probable fragment and isobars with nuclear charges higher than that of the most probable fragment.

Out of the 83 chains from mass numbers 76 to 158, there are only 20 chains in which isobars beginning from stable members up to the most probable fragments have been discovered. The total number of β -active nuclei from the stable members up to most probable fragments in the 83 chains are 273. Of these only 144 nuclei have so far been discovered. We can therefore expect 129 β -active nuclei in this region.

There are, however, some series, say series with mass number 145, $54 \text{ Xe } 145 \rightarrow 55 \text{ Cs } 145 \rightarrow 56 \text{ Ba } 145 \rightarrow 57 \text{ La } 145 \rightarrow 58 \text{ Ce } 145 \rightarrow 59 \text{ Pr } 145 \rightarrow 60 \text{ Nd } 145$ in which the most probable fragment is $57 \text{ La } 145$, but the series has been traced up to $\text{Xe } 145$. Though the yields of nuclei with charge numbers lower than that of the most probable fragment is very low and the life periods are very short, yet we can expect three nuclei per series in the 83 chains mentioned above, provided the experimental technique to identify them is developed. On this basis the probable number of nuclei with charge number lower than those the most probable fragments is 249; but only 18 amongst them have so far been known. Therefore the number of nuclei with nuclear charges lower than those of the most probable fragments still to be discovered is 231.

From similar considerations, as stated above, a fragment with a charge number higher at least by three units than that of the most probable fragment can also be detected. Most of such nuclei fall in between most probable fragments and stable members, and number of such nuclei has already been mentioned. But on counting the isobars in series up to three units of charge higher than those of the most probable fragment, we meet with some series where there are active nuclei with charge numbers higher than those of the stable members (vide Table III). The number of expected nuclei in this region is only 27 of which three have already been detected in fission. So the number of expected active nuclei in this region is 24 and some of these may be β^+ active.

From what has been said it can be inferred that the total number of active nuclei (in between mass numbers 76 and 158) expected in fission is 549 and only 165 among them are known. On this basis the number of nuclei awaiting discovery is 384. So we note that more than $\frac{2}{3}$ of the expected active nuclei in fission have not yet been discovered.

It should be stated that the series with mass numbers 72 to 75, though observed in fission, have not been the subject matter of our discussions. This is because there is no evidence of any heavy chain corresponding to any one of them. The absence of any heavy chain may be either due to low fission frequency and difficulties in the separation of the rare-earths which are most probable fragments here or it may so happen that these mass numbers may be derived from ternary fission, a phenomenon which cannot have any relation with the complementary series.

It should be pointed out that in a few cases, as will be evidenced from Table I and Fig. 1, that in order to generalise the fission mechanism, some allowance has been granted to error in yield determinations. The probable percentage of error with experimental details are not yet published. Specially in the heavy group, from mass numbers 130 to 134, the low values in yields against corresponding values for the light series are significant. It should be mentioned that the total yield in the light group is 100.3%,

whereas in the heavy group, as the figures stand, it is 94.8%. This 5% loss in the heavy group can reasonably be assumed to be due to error in yield values in mass numbers 130-134.

The above treatments as regards detecting complementary series is rather free from adverse criticism and the hypothesis as regards the most probable conjugate charge numbers is based on inferences from experimental observation but that the mass/charge ratio values of the most probable conjugate fragments are equal, is however, an assumption. This from a chemist's point of view is a subject experimental verification of which requires determination of the yield values of a chain with different β -disintegrating charge numbers. However, predictions that have been made, open up a wide scope of investigation in this line.

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